

Q.1 Give the singular forms of the underlined plural nouns, and the plural forms of the underlined singular nouns. Do not rewrite the sentences.

1. The woman complained to the policeman.
2. I forgot to put the potatoes in the soup.
3. Please arrange the benches neatly.
4. Slice the mango for the pudding.
5. The deer ran away on seeing the lions.
6. The boy saw the thieves entering the house.
7. Suman put the toys back on the shelf.
8. The farmer drove the oxen into the barn.
9. After dinner, the child went to bed.
10. We heard the echoes of our voices in the hall.
11. Naheed put her feet into a tub of hot water.
12. We have complained about the bully.
13. Look at the red, juicy apples on the tree!
14. We saw smoke coming out of the windows.
15. I am going to visit the famous library.

Q.2 Fill in the blanks with the plurals of the nouns given in brackets.

1. There are many _____(country) in the world.
2. The _____(lady) had the _____(key) to their cars.
3. We saw four _____(donkey) at the farm.
4. Rohan picked _____(daisy) and _____(lily) from the garden.
5. Our _____(diary) were left behind in school.
6. Jack has been to five _____(city) with this troupe.
7. The children received free _____(toy) on Children's Day.
8. _____(baby) need special attention and care

Q.3 Use the plurals of the words given in brackets to complete the sentences.

1. All the _____wore black hats. (man)
2. Be sure to brush your_____ after eating anything sweet. (tooth)
3. Look at those _____sitting under the tree. (woman)
4. The _____flew in a V-shaped pattern. (goose)
5. He wiped his _____with a dry towel. (foot)

Q 4: Write the plural form of the following nouns.

7. a) Cat
b) Dog
c) Baby
d) Book
e) Bus
f) Leaf
g) Tooth
h) Man
i) Woman
j) Child

8. : Rewrite the following sentences by changing the singular nouns to their plural forms.

9. a) The cat is on the roof.
 b) She has a small dog.
 c) The baby is sleeping.
 d) I read a book.
 e) The bus is coming.
10. : **Fill in the blanks with the appropriate singular or plural form of the noun:**
11. a) I have two _____.
 b) The _____ is flying in the sky.
 c) My friend has many _____.
 d) The _____ are sitting on the branch.
 e) There are three _____ in the garden.
12. : **Choose the correct plural form of the noun:**
13. a) Tooth – teeth/teeths
 b) Sheep – sheeps/sheepes
 c) Child – childs/children
 d) Mouse – mouses/mice
 e) Leaf – leafs/leaves
14. **Q 12: Rewrite the sentences by changing the singular nouns to their plural forms.**
15. a) The cat is sleeping on the chair.
 b) She has a big dog.
 c) The baby is crying.
 d) He read a book.
 e) The bus is stopping.

Q.15 Rewrite the sentences by changing the nouns into plurals. Make changes in verbs and articles where necessary.

16. The child went to the shop with the woman.

17. The leaf of tulsi is good for health.

18. My sister ate the peach and threw the pit in the dustbin.

19. The minister met the man who wanted to donate clothes.

20. The house had no light on.

21. The cat ate the mouse and ran away.

